

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of *n*-Butylamine by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III) Catalysed by Cu(II) Ions

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Kinetics of oxidation of *n*-butylamine by alkaline potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) in presence of Cu(II) as catalyst has been studied. The reaction has been found to have first order dependence in butylamine, oxidant, sodium hydroxide and the catalyst concentration. A positive salt effect and pronounced negative effect of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ ions is observed on the reaction rate. Thermodynamic parameters have been determined. The probable mechanism has been suggested.

OXIDATION of a variety of organic compounds by potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) has been studied by a number of workers.¹⁻⁴ OsO_4 has been widely employed as catalyst in the oxidation reaction in alkaline medium⁵⁻⁸. However, very few cases of catalysis by Cu(II) ion in this redox system are reported in literature. Recently, I. R. Wilson⁹⁻¹¹ and coworkers have investigated the role of Cu(II) ions in the oxidation of cystine and related thiols and hydroxylamine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III). The kinetics of oxidation of *n*-butylamine by potassium peroxydisulphate¹² has been studied by previous workers. The present paper incorporates the results of kinetics of oxidation of *n*-butylamine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) in presence of Cu(II) ions as catalyst.

Materials and Method

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) used was B.D.H. AnalaR and its standard solution was prepared in doubly distilled water. Its strength was checked iodometrically¹³. All other chemicals, *n*-butylamine, copper sulphate, sodium hydroxide and potassium hexacyanoferrate(III), etc., were either A. R. grade or extra pure quality and their standard solutions were prepared by direct weighing in doubly distilled water. The solution of sodium hydroxide was always standardised before use.

The kinetics was followed by estimating the decrease in hexacyanoferrate(III) concentration with time iodometrically. The results are interpreted in terms of initial rate of the reaction to avoid the complexities which may arise due to interference by the products.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry :

To determine the number of moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) reacted per mole of *n*-butylamine,

a known amount of *n*-butylamine was mixed with 20 times its molar concentration of alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) along with Cu(II) as catalyst and the mixture was kept for sufficient time at 60° for the completion of the reaction. It was noted that 4 moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) are consumed per mole of *n*-butylamine to give such products which are not further oxidised. The stoichiometry thus may be represented by the equation

For quantitative estimating of butyric acid 100 ml of reaction mixture containing 0.005 mole each of butylamine and potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) at $[\text{NaOH}] = 2.0 \text{ M}$ along with copper sulphate as catalyst were kept in a thermostat at 60° till the reaction was complete. The mixture was then neutralised and subjected to distillation in presence of small excess of sulphuric acid in order to decompose sodium salt of butyric acid present in the mixture. The results are recorded in Table 1(a).

TABLE 1(a)

Mole of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ reacted	Moles of butylamine reacted calculated stoichiometrically	Moles of butyric acid estimated	Moles of butyric acid calculated stoichiometrically
5.0×10^{-3}	1.25×10^{-3}	1.24×10^{-3}	1.25×10^{-3}

Kinetics :

The kinetic investigation was carried out at several initial concentrations of the reactants, keeping other variable parameters constant. First order dependence in hexacyanoferrate(III) was followed at all concentrations of the reactants. (Fig. 1). The pseudo first order rate constants were computed from the slope of log concentration—time plot.

Fig. 1. Hexacyanoferrate(III) Dependence
 n -Butylamine = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, NaOH = $2.0 M$,
 $CuSO_4 = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, Temp. $45^\circ C$
 (a) $Fe(CN)_6^{3-} = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, (b) $Fe(CN)_6^{3-} = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$,
 (c) $Fe(CN)_6^{3-} = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, (d) $Fe(CN)_6^{3-} = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$,
 (e) $Fe(CN)_6^{3-} = 4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Table 1 incorporates the value of first order constant at different temperatures.

A plot of $\log k_1$ vs. T^{-1} gave a straight line. From the mean slope of the Arrhenius plot $\Delta E = 11.0$ K cal and $\Delta S = -43.9$ cal deg^{-1} mole $^{-1}$ have been calculated.

Dependence of Initial Rate on the Concentration of the Reactants :

Tables 2-5 represent the dependence of the initial reaction rate on the concentrations of the reactants. Order with respect to each of the reactants is found to be unity.

The table 6 shows that the reaction rate increases by the addition of salts like potassium chloride, potassium sulphate, sodium chloride and sodium acetate. Potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) has a retarding effect indicating that the step generating hexacyanoferrate(II) in the mechanism is a reversible one.

Mechanism :

The effect of salt on the rate of oxidation of n -butylamine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III), being positive and entropy of activation being negative ($\Delta S = -43.9$ cal deg^{-1} mole $^{-1}$) it seems likely that the rate determining step involves reaction between similarly charged ions or between the negatively charged ion and dipole.

TABLE 1

$[n\text{-Butylamine}] = [Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[CuSO_4] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[NaOH] = 2.0 M$					
Temperature $^\circ C$	40	45	50	55	60
$k_1 \times 10^4$ (sec $^{-1}$)	0.88	1.03	1.42	1.95	2.50

TABLE 2— n -BUTYLAMINE DEPENDENCE

$[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[CuSO_4] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[NaOH] = 2.0 M$, Temp. $45^\circ C$						
$[Butylamine] \times 10^3$ mole l^{-1}	0.2	0.4	0.6	1.0	1.5	2.0
I.R. $\times 10^4$ mole l^{-1} min $^{-1}$	0.61	1.24	1.90	3.10	4.64	6.21
I.R. $\times 10^4$ [Butylamine]	3.05	3.12	3.16	3.10	3.10	3.10

TABLE 3—HEXACYANOFERRATE(III) DEPENDENCE

$[n\text{-Butylamine}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Fe(CN)_6^{3-}] \times 10^3$ mole l^{-1}	$[NaOH] = 2.0 M$		$[CuSO_4] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$		Temp. $45^\circ C$
	1.0	1.5	2.0	3.0	4.0
I.R. $\times 10^4$ mole l^{-1} min $^{-1}$	3.10	3.72	5.16	7.74	11.84
I.R. $\times 10^4$ [Fe(CN) $_6^{3-}]$	3.10	2.48	2.58	2.58	2.96

TABLE 4—COPPER SULPHATE DEPENDENCE

[<i>n</i> -Butylamine]=[Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻]=1.0×10 ⁻³ M,	[NaOH]=2.0M,		Temp. 45°C		
[CuSO ₄]×10 ⁴ mole l ⁻¹	3	5	6	8	10
I.R.×10 ⁴ mole l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	2.07	3.10	4.30	5.71	6.65
I.R. [CuSO ₄]	0.690	0.620	0.717	0.716	0.665

TABLE 5—SODIUM HYDROXIDE DEPENDENCE

[<i>n</i> -Butylamine]=[Fe(CN) ₆ ³⁻]=1.0×10 ⁻³ M,	[CuSO ₄]=5.0×10 ⁻⁴ M,		Temp. 45°C		
NaOH mole l ⁻¹	1.2	1.4	1.6	2.0	2.4
I.R.×10 ⁴ mole l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹	1.95	2.95	2.65	3.10	3.84
I.R.×10 ⁴ [NaOH]	0.162	0.166	0.166	0.155	0.160

TABLE 6—SALT EFFECT

[*n*-Butylamine]=[Fe(CN)₆³⁻]=1.0×10⁻³M, [NaOH]=2.0M,
[CuSO₄]=5.0×10⁻⁴M, Temp. 45°C

Salt	Mole l ⁻¹	I.R.×10 ⁴ mole l ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
Nil	—	3.10
KCl	0.10	3.51
	0.20	3.92
K ₂ SO ₄	0.05	3.68
	0.10	4.03
K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	0.025	0.10
	0.05	0.05
NaCl	0.10	3.15
	0.20	3.45
CH ₃ COONa	0.10	3.45
	0.20	3.74

Taking into consideration the kinetics data obtained the scheme—(i) is proposed for oxidation of *n*-butylamine.

Steps (4) and (6) are similar to those as suggested by G. Chandra¹⁴ and K. D. Pathak¹⁵ for the oxidation of amino acid by peroxydisulphate and hexacyanoferrate(III).

In the presence of limited oxidant concentration CH₃CH₂CH₂CH₂NHOH (step 4) may be the terminating step. However, with excess of the oxidant CH₃CH₂CH₂CH₂NHOH is further oxidised to butyric acid.

Scheme (i)

Step (3) may also be explained in two steps

Cu(I) formed is rapidly oxidised to Cu(II)

The formation of Cu(I) and its ready oxidation to Cu(II) has also been shown by Glenn J. Bridgert⁹ and I. R. Wilson.

It is noteworthy to point out that a step similar to (1) has also been proposed by S. P. Musheran and co-workers¹⁶ and P. S. Radhakrishnamurti and co-workers¹⁷ for the oxidation reaction of hydrazine and aniline by hexacyanoferrate(III).

Step (1) is the slowest and rate controlling which finds support from positive salt effect and negative entropy of activation. The negative value of entropy of activation also supports¹⁸ incorporation of the water molecule in the reaction sequence (3).

The pronounced negative effect of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ ions on the reaction rate supports the reversible nature of the step (1).

From the above scheme the following rate law equation may be derived by applying steady state treatment to the various intermediates.

$$\frac{-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{Amine}][\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Cu}(\text{II})]}{k_{-1} k_{-2} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}] + k_3 [\text{Cu}(\text{II})] \{k_{-1} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] + [\text{OH}^-]\}}$$

Since alkali concentration is high and $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ concentration is low in the initial stages of the reaction the inequality $k_2 [\text{OH}^-] \gg k_{-1} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ may be valid.

$$\frac{-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{Amine}][\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Cu}(\text{II})]}{k_{-1} k_{-2} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}] + k_3 k_3 [\text{Cu}(\text{II})][\text{OH}^-]}$$

Further, if the equilibrium (1) and (2) are more towards the left the inequality $k_{-1} k_{-2} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}] \gg k_2 k_3 [\text{Cu}(\text{II})][\text{OH}^-]$ may also be valid. Hence the final rate law, after applying the above approximation for the initial reaction, reduces to

$$\frac{-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{Amine}][\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Cu}(\text{II})]}{k_{-1} k_{-2} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}]}$$

The derived rate law reveals that the oxidation of *n*-butylamine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) would have first order dependence in each of the reactants and the added $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ would retard the reaction and these facts have been confirmed experimentally.

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